

3-D BOUNDARY ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF MICROMECHANICS PROBLEMS IN METAL GRAIN REINFORCED RESINS

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1. INTRODUCTION

The dies used for blow molding, injection molding, compression molding and transfer molding of plastics are now made of Al or Fe grain reinforced epoxy resin or phenolic resin in stead of steel or aluminium alloys, which makes the die making peoriod shorter and greatly reduces the cost and the weight of the dies ¹. The modulus of grain reinforced composites is much lower than metal materials at the die working temperature, which may lead to larger deformations when the dies are subjected to their working loads. This would influence the quality of plastic products directly. It is important for the applications of grain reinforced composites to the die making area that the modulus of the new material with different volumn ratios should be predicted accurately at different temperature.

many micromechanics models, such as the parallel phases, the series, the disperse, the Hirsch's, the Counto's and the Hashin's models, have been proposed for the modulus calculation of grain reinforced composites ². But there exist larger deviations between their computing results and experiment results because the random distribution of the grains in the 3-D domain of the matrix was not considered in all these models. A boundary element technique combining the theory of statistics is presented in this paper for the modulus calculation of grain reinforced composites at higher temperature. The modulus of epoxy reinforced with sphere shaped Al grain at the working temperature of injection molding was tested. Good coincidence was found between the experiment result and the computed result by the boundary element method.

2. BOUNDARY ELEMENT METHOD WITH SUBREGIONS AND CONDENSATION TECHNIQUE

The boundary integral equation of boundary value problems of elastostatics with no body force may be written as follows ³

$$[C_1]\{U_1\} - \int_{\Gamma} [P^*]\{U\}d\Gamma = \int_{\Gamma} [U^*]\{P\}d\Gamma \quad (1)$$

where $\{U\}$ and $\{P\}$ are the boundary displacements and tractions respectively $[U^*]$ and $[P^*]$ are the displacements and tractions corresponding to the Kelvin's fundamental solution. Finite elements were plotted on the boundary of the domain and then Eq. (1) is discretized. Taking each node on the boundary as the source point in the fundamental solution, one obtains the system of equations

$$[H]\{U\} = [G]\{P\} \quad (2)$$

where $\{U\}$ and $\{P\}$ are the node displacements and tractions respectively, $[H]$ and $[G]$ are corresponding coefficient matrices.

Let a 3-D domain Ω consists of a continuous phase (the elastic matrix) and M elastic

inclusions with different phase (the grain), see Fig.1. The domain Ω was divided into $M+1$ subregions: the number for the matrix is zero, and the numbers for the other subregions are $1, 2, \dots, M$ respectively. All the boundaries including the common boundaries between these subregions were discretized and then, a system of equation like Eq.(2) may be written for each subregion. They are listed as following

$$\begin{aligned}
 & [H_0^0 \ H_0^0 \ H_1^0 \ H_2^0 \ \dots \ H_n^0] [U_0^0 \ U_0^0 \ U_1^1 \ U_2^2 \ \dots \ U_n^n]^T = \\
 & [G_0^0 \ G_0^0 \ G_1^0 \ G_2^0 \ \dots \ G_n^0] [P_0^0 \ P_0^0 \ P_1^1 \ P_2^2 \ \dots \ P_n^n]^T \\
 & [H_0^1] \{U_1^0\} = [G_0^1] \{P_1^0\} \\
 & [H_0^2] \{U_2^0\} = [G_0^2] \{P_2^0\} \\
 & \vdots \\
 & [H_0^n] \{U_n^0\} = [G_0^n] \{P_n^0\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where H_k^1 and G_k^1 ($k, l=0 \sim M$) represent the submatrices in the coefficient matrices $[H]$ and $[G]$ of the k th subregion corresponding to the boundary adjacent to the l th subregion, \bar{H}^0 and \bar{G}^0 represent the submatrix in the coefficient matrices $[H]$ and $[G]$ of the 0 th subregion corresponding to the known node displacements and node tractions, and H_0^0 and G_0^0 corresponding to the unknown, U_k^1 and P_k^1 ($k, l=0 \sim M$) represent the unknown node displacements and node tractions on the boundary of the k th subregion adjacent to the l th subregion.

On the common boundaries of all the subregions, exist the following conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_k^1 &= U_1^k \quad (k, l=0 \sim M) \\
 P_k^1 &= P_1^k \quad (k, l=0 \sim M)
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Substituting Eq. (4) into Eq.(3) results in the general system of equations

$$\left[\begin{array}{cc|cccccc}
 G_0^0 & H_0^0 & H_1^0 & -G_1^0 & H_2^0 & -G_2^0 & \dots & H_M^0 & -G_M^0 \\
 \hline
 0 & 0 & H_0^1 & G_0^1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & H_0^2 & G_0^2 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\
 \vdots & \vdots \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & H_0^M & G_0^M
 \end{array} \right] \begin{bmatrix} P_0^0 \\ U_0^0 \\ U_1^1 \\ P_1^1 \\ \vdots \\ U_0^M \\ P_0^M \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{H}^0 & \bar{U}^0 + \bar{G}^0 \bar{P}^0 \\ \hline 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{5}$$

Eq.(5) could be written in an abbreviated form

$$[A]\{X\} = \{F\} \tag{6}$$

One may obtain all the unknown node displacements and node tractions by solving Eq.(6).

Actually, only the node displacements U_0^0 on the outer boundary are wanted. Dividing the matrices in Eq.(6) into submatrices shown in Eq.(5) by dotted lines, one may rewrite matrix $[A]$ as

$$[A] = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} \end{bmatrix} \tag{7}$$

where $A_{11} = [G_0^0 \ H_0^0]$. Let

$$[B] = [A]^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11} & B_{12} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where B_{11} and B_{22} are in the same order as A_{11} and A_{22} . Obviously, one need only compute B_{11} and B_{12} to obtain U_0^o . Utilizing $A_{21}=[0]$, the following may be derived

$$\left. \begin{aligned} B_{11} &= A_{11}^{-1} + WR^{-1}P \\ B_{12} &= -WR^{-1} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} W &= A_{11}^{-1}A_{12} \\ P &= A_{21}A_{11}^{-1} \\ R &= A_{22} - PA_{12} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

In general, it will save much compute time to obtain U_0^o through Eq.(9) and Eq.(10) in stead of solving Eq.(6).

3. EXAMPLE FOR COMPUTING THE MODULUS OF GRAIN REINFORCED COMPOSITE

Take a typical element from the material of epoxy resin reinforced with 100/200 μ sphere shaped Al grain. Suppose there are three Al spheres included in the element and let the volum ratio of Al to epoxy in the element be equal to that in the given material. Let the element be subjected to load Q uniformly distributed on its upper surface, and displacement constraint on its four lateral surfaces (see Fig.2). According to reference [4], the modulus of Al can be expressed as a function of temperature

$$E_f = 6934.5 + 4.3804 \times 10^{-2}T^2 - 5.1570 \times 10^{-4}T^3 + 8.2148 \times 10^{-7}T^4 \quad (11)$$

The temperature of thermo-deformation of the epoxy resin solidified by MPD agent is 155°C which is much higher than the working temperature of the injection dies (90°C). One may take the modulus of the epoxy matrix as $E_m=320\text{kg/mm}^2$, and consider it as linear elastomer approximately.

The typical element was divided into four subregions and all the boundaries are discretized. To save more compute time, triangular constant elements are used. The total number of the constant elements is 144 (see Fig.3). The average displacement in the load direction on the upper surface of the typical element may be obtained by the method described in section 2, and then the modulus of the composite material can be calculated according to the value of the load and the size of the typical element.

It is found that the modulus computed by this method varies with the position coordinates of the spheres. The coordinates of the sphere centres were randomly given 50 times by the computer and the boundary element meshes were plotted automatically. Repeating the modulus calculation for each of the 50 times, one obtains 50 values of the modulus. After frequency grouping, a histogram for above data is made and the frequency distribution curve is plotted (Fig.4). Let the computed frequency distribution curve be approximated to the Weibull frequency distribution function

$$F(E) = \frac{b}{E_* - E_o} \left[\frac{E - E_o}{E_* - E_o} \right]^{b-1} \exp \left\{ - \left[\frac{E - E_o}{E_* - E_o} \right]^b \right\} \quad (12)$$

then the parameters E_o , E_* and b in Eq.(12) are determined. The mean of the weibull variable may be written as

$$E_c = \int_{E_0}^{\infty} \frac{Eb}{E_* - E_0} \left[\frac{E - E_0}{E_* - E_0} \right]^{b-1} \exp \left\{ - \left[\frac{E - E_0}{E_* - E_0} \right]^b \right\} dE \quad (13)$$

Using variable transformation, one obtains

$$E_0 = E_0 + (E_* - E_0) \Gamma(1+b) \quad (14)$$

where Γ represents Γ function. The value of E_0 computed from Eq.(14) may be considered as the modulus of the Al grain reinforced epoxy resin at the temperature when the injection die works. The variance of the Weibull variable may be written as follows

$$\sigma^2 = (E_* - E_0)^2 \left[\Gamma \left(1 + \frac{2}{b} \right) - \Gamma^2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{b} \right) \right] \quad (15)$$

The value of σ^2 may become smaller if one takes more sphere grains in the typical element.

4. EXPERIMENT

Following the testing standard ISO 604 for thermosetting plastics, 12 test specimen were made in the same volumn ratio as in the above example. High temperature gauges was used for the load and the temperature of the specimen was kept by a controled electricity heating circle. The value of the modulus measured may be evaluated

$$E = \frac{\Delta \sigma}{\Delta \epsilon} \quad (16)$$

where $\Delta \sigma$ and $\Delta \epsilon$ are the increments of the stress and the strain measured respectively.

For 100/200 μ sphere shaped Al grain reinforced epoxy resin with 50% volume ratio, at the die temperature of 80°C for the injection molding of Amide 1010[7], the modulus computed by the boundary element method is $E_c=1160.\text{kg/mm}^2$ and the measured value is $E=965.12\text{kg/mm}^2$.

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSIONS

The advantages of the boundary element method are simple data preparing, easy to produce element mesh, good accuracy and shorter compute time etc. The numerical technique proposed in this paper for modulus calculation of grain reinforced composites, combining the boundary element method and statistic theory, may count in the random distribution of the reinforcing grains in the matrix .The computed result for the sphere shaped Al grain reinforced epoxy resin is found in good coincidence with the experiment, which shows the feasibility of this technique.

The deviation of the computed result may come from two aspects. The number of repeatedly computed times is too small or the working temperatuer of the die is so high such that the epoxy resin no long keeps linear elastic. The former may be avoided by taking the number of computed times larger than 50 or taking more inclusions in the typical element. The visioelastic behavior should be considered in the calculations when the second situation occurs.

REFERENCES

1. SinKeits and Yie Soujin, Dies of Plastic Products, Light Industrial Publisher, 1985.
2. Robert N., Hand Book of Composite Materials, Prentice-Hall, Inc., New Jersey, 1983, P296-308.
3. Brebbia, C.A., Tells, J.C.F. and Wrobel, L.C., Boundary Element Techniques, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1984, P253-275.
4. Ying Dishin, On Fatigue Behavior of Al Alloys at High Temperature, master these's of Luoyang Institute of Technology, 1988.

5. Beijing Institute of GRP, Hand Book of GRP Design, China Construction Industry Publisher, 1986, P35, P161.
6. Go Zhinton, Statistic Theory of Fatigue, National Defence Industry Publisher, 1986, P82-90
7. Meter and Instrument Bureau of the ministry of Machine Building Industry, Injection and Compression Molding of Plastics, Machine Building Industry Publisher, 1985, P236-237.

Fig.1 Domain Ω with M Inclusions

Fig.2 Typical Element

Fig.3 Boundary Element Mesh

Fig.4 Weibull Distribution Function